

Assessing Land Use and Land Cover Changes in Waghur Basin: A Remote Sensing and Machine Learning Approach for Sustainable Land Management

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the importance of studying land use and land cover changes in densely populated countries, with a specific focus on the Waghur Basin in India. It emphasizes the significance of remote sensing techniques for detecting and analyzing these changes. The study uses remote sensing data and machine learning algorithms to classify and analyze land use and land cover patterns in the Waghur Basin from 1990 to 2022. The results reveal significant changes in land utilization, including an increase in agricultural land and a decrease in forest and bare land areas. These changes have implications for the environment and land management. The manuscript underscores the need for addressing deforestation, promoting sustainable agriculture practices, managing urbanization, and preserving water resources for long-term sustainability. It emphasizes the importance of understanding and monitoring land use and land cover changes for effective land management and conservation strategies.

Keywords: Land use Change detection; Artificial intelligence; Machin Learning; Remote Sensing; GIS

Introduction:

In an era of growing population pressures on available land, the importance of land utilization and land use has become a critical concern in densely populated countries, notably India. This heightened significance arises from historical investigations that sought to evaluate different facets of land use, especially in relation to agricultural cultivation, with the overarching goal of optimizing land productivity to its fullest potential (Singh, 1967). The transformation of land use and land cover (LULC) stands as a major issue within the global environmental landscape. A clarion call for substantial research into the dynamics of land use changes emerged during the 1972 Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment and resurfaced two decades later during the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED). In tandem with these international discussions, the International Geosphere and Biosphere Programme (IGBP) and the International Human Dimension Programme (IHDP) joined forces to establish a working group that would set an agenda and bolster research endeavors in the realm of LULC changes.

Land use/land cover mapping emerges as a cornerstone, integrating various parameters to establish a comprehensive framework for the assessment of land and water resources, supporting diverse developmental indices. Land use embodies the manifold human activities and the diverse purposes they serve across the landscape, while land cover encompasses natural features such as vegetation, water bodies, geological elements, artificial structures, and other noticeable features on the Earth's surface (NRSA, 1989). This assemblage of biotic and abiotic components on the Earth's surface represents one of the most critical elements within the Earth system. Land cover refers to what blankets the Earth's surface, while land use delineates how that cover is adapted and utilized. Land cover includes water bodies, snow, grasslands, forests, and bare soil, whereas land use encompasses agricultural land, urban development, recreational zones, wildlife management areas, and more.

These papers collectively provide information on land use and land cover. Dvivedi 2020 explains that land use refers to human activities on a particular piece of land, while land cover describes the types of features present on the Earth's surface. Kumar 2015 further emphasizes that land cover includes biotic and abiotic components, such as water, snow, grassland, forest, and bare soil, while land use describes how the land cover is modified. Verburg 2003 adds that land cover change involves the complete replacement of one cover type by another, while land use changes also include modifications within the same cover type. Skidmore 2002 highlights the environmental impacts associated with land conversion, including habitat loss, fragmentation, and the introduction of invasive species. In summary, land use refers to human activities on land, while land cover describes the types of features present on the Earth's surface.

These papers collectively discuss the use of remote sensing techniques for land use and land cover change detection. Mohammed 2017 highlights the effectiveness of remote sensing in evaluating and monitoring changes in land use and land cover over time. Kuldeep 2017 focuses on detecting land use changes in Dehradun Valley using satellite images and topographic maps. Pareta 2014 presents a GIS and remote sensing approach for modeling land use and land cover change in the industrial region of Baddi town. Harish 2017 emphasizes the importance of remote sensing and change detection methods in studying land use and land cover changes. Overall, these papers demonstrate the utility of remote sensing techniques in detecting and analyzing land use and land cover changes over time.

In essence, remote sensing satellite data, with its multi-resolution and multispectral capabilities, furnishes spatial information across varying levels of detail, encompassing built-up areas, agricultural lands, forests, wastelands, and water bodies, among others. The land cover and land use maps crafted from multi-date and multispectral data sources offer an array of spatial information, proving indispensable for change detection studies (Burrough, 1986).

This study aims to chart the evolution of land use and land cover in the Waghur Basin spanning the years from 1990 to 2022, with the primary objective of detecting changes in land use patterns. Remote sensing data assumes a pivotal role in this endeavor, thanks to its unique capacity for synoptic observation, repetitive coverage, and real-time data acquisition. Digital data, in the form of Landsat satellite imagery, enables precise categorization of various land cover and land use types, while simultaneously contributing to the essential spatial data infrastructure (SDI) necessary

for monitoring urban expansion and change detection studies (Lo, 1981; Mukherjee, 1987; and Quarmby & Cushine, 1989).

Study Area

This particular study focuses on the meso-scale watershed known as the Waghur Basin, which extends between 20° 27' 32" to 21° 05' 43" N latitude and 74° 30' 7" to 76° 05' 11" E longitude. The study rigorously considers five primary land use categories: agricultural land, forested areas, built-up regions, bare land, and water bodies.

Aim

The aim of the research is to detect and analyze the land use and land cover changes in the Waghur Basin in India from 1990 to 2022 using remote sensing data and machine learning algorithms. The manuscript emphasizes the importance of understanding and monitoring land use and land cover changes for effective land management and conservation strategies.

Objectives

- To study land use and land cover changes in the Waghur Basin in India from 1990 to 2022.
- To analyze the implications of land use changes on the environment and land management.
- To use remote sensing data and machine learning algorithms to classify and analyze land use and land cover patterns.
- To create accurate land use and land cover maps to support decision-making and policy development.

Methods and Material

The aim of this paper is to detect the Land use / Land cover change from 1990 to 2022. The multi-spectral satellite data is used for supervised classification for prepare Land use map. The data utilized is given in the following tables for the years 1990 and 2022. ArcGIS Pro 3.0 and ERDAS 2022 have been used for geographical analysis, integration, and presentation of the spatial and non-spatial data for land cover / land use change detection. So, these tools are more effective for monitoring and modeling for land cover / land use changes. Following are the detail steps to prepare LULC map data using Machin learning. Land use and land cover (LULC) classification by machine learning methods involves the use of algorithms and models to automatically categorize and label different land cover and land use types within satellite or remote sensing imagery. Here is an explanation of the steps involved in the classification of LULC using machine learning:

- Start by acquiring remote sensing data, typically in the form of satellite imagery. These images may include different spectral bands, such as visible, infrared, and thermal data.
- Preprocess the acquired data by removing noise, atmospheric distortions, and any artifacts that might affect the classification accuracy.
- Perform radiometric and geometric corrections to ensure the data is consistent and aligned.
- Split the data into two sets: training data and testing data. The training data is used to train the machine learning model, while the testing data is used to evaluate its performance.

- Extract relevant features from the remote sensing data. These features can be spectral, textural, or spatial in nature and provide information about the land cover and land use characteristics.
- Manually or semi-automatically label regions of interest in the training dataset with their corresponding land cover or land use categories. These labels serve as ground truth for the machine learning algorithm.
- For the classification of data researcher choose Support Vector Machines (SVM) appropriate machine learning algorithm for the classification task
- Use the labeled training data to train the machine learning model. The model learns to distinguish between different land cover and land use classes based on the extracted features.
- Assess the model's performance using the testing dataset. Common evaluation metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrices.
- Apply post-processing techniques to refine the classification results. This may involve filtering out small, spurious classifications or smoothing boundaries between land cover classes.
- Create LULC maps by applying the trained machine learning model to the entire remote sensing dataset. The model assigns each pixel or region in the image to a specific land cover or land use category by using ArcGIS Pro software.
- Validate the LULC classification results through ground truth data or field surveys to confirm the accuracy of the classification.

Results and Discussion

The Land use maps of Waghur basin for both the years reveal five classes of Land use. Viz Land under agriculture, Land under forest, Land under Built-up area, bare land and Land under water bodies. The classified images obtained after preprocessing and supervised classification which are showing the land use and land cover of the Waghur basin are given in the following figure 2 & 3. These images provide the information about the land use pattern of the study area.

Table 1 Spatio-Temporal distribution of Land use of Waghur basin

LULC	Year 1990 Area (sq.km)	Area in %	Year 2022 Area (sq.km)	Area in %
Forest Land	310.71	12.50	283.82	11.42
Agriculture Land	987.45	39.74	1389.13	55.90
Bare Land	1152.5	46.38	744.5	29.96
Settlement	19.30	0.78	35.26	1.42
Water Bodies	15.04	0.61	32.29	1.30
Total Area	2485.00	100	2485.00	100

(Source: Landsat 5 Satellite Image)

Figure 1 Land use/ Land cover map of Waghur basin 1990

(Source: Landsat 8 Satellite Image)

*Figure 1 Land use/ Land cover map of Waghur basin 2022**Table 2 Land use Change Detection during 1990 - 2022*

LULC	Year 1990 Area (sq.km)	Year 2022 Area(sq.km)	Increase Area(sq.km)	Decrease Area(sq.km)
Forest Land	310.71	283.82		26.89
Agriculture Land	987.45	1389.13	401.68	
Bare Land	1152.50	744.50		408.00
Settlement	19.30	35.26	15.96	
Water Bodies	15.04	32.29	17.25	
Total Area	2485.00	2485.00		

The table (1) below provides a comparative analysis of land use and land cover (LULC) between the years 1990 and 2022 in terms of area (in square kilometers) and the percentage of each land category relative to the total area. Between 1990 and 2022, forest land area decreased from 310.71 sq.km (12.50% of the total area) to 283.82 sq.km (11.42% of the total area). This indicates a reduction in forested areas over this period. Agriculture land witnessed a significant increase from 987.45 sq.km (39.74% of the total area) in 1990 to 1389.13 sq.km (55.90% of the total area) in 2022. This reflects a substantial expansion of agricultural activities. Bare land, which constituted 46.38% of the total area in 1990 (1152.5 sq.km), decreased to 29.96% (744.5 sq.km) in 2022. This reduction may suggest land use changes, such as urbanization or reforestation. Settlement areas increased slightly from 19.30 sq.km (0.78% of the total area) in 1990 to 35.26 sq.km (1.42% of the total area) in 2022. This indicates modest urban expansion or growth in residential areas. Water bodies also saw an increase, with their area expanding from 15.04 sq.km (0.61% of the total area) in 1990 to 32.29 sq.km (1.30% of the total area) in 2022. This may result from factors like water reservoirs or changes in natural water bodies.

The LULC changes over the analyzed years demonstrate shifts in land utilization, with agriculture expanding significantly at the expense of forest land and bare land. These changes may have implications for the environment, including habitat loss and alterations in local climate and ecosystems. Further detailed investigations are required to understand the underlying causes and potential consequences of these changes and to inform land management and conservation strategies.

The table (2) below presents changes in land use and land cover (LULC) from the year 1990 to 2022, indicating both increases and decreases in area (in square kilometers). Forest land saw a decrease in area from 310.71 sq.km in 1990 to 283.82 sq.km in 2022. This indicates a reduction of 26.89 sq.km in forested areas over this period, possibly due to factors such as deforestation or natural habitat changes. Agriculture land experienced a significant increase from 987.45 sq.km in 1990 to 1389.13 sq.km in 2022. This represents a substantial expansion of 401.68 sq.km, reflecting increased agricultural activities or land conversion for farming. Bare land decreased in area from 1152.50 sq.km in 1990 to 744.50 sq.km in 2022. This indicates a reduction of 408.00 sq.km in bare land, possibly due to urbanization, reforestation, or other land use changes. Settlement areas increased by 15.96 sq.km, from 19.30 sq.km in 1990 to 35.26 sq.km in 2022. This suggests modest

(Source: ERDAS & ArcGIS Analysis)

Figure 2 Land use/ Land cover change detection map

urban expansion or growth in residential areas over the years. Water bodies witnessed an increase in area from 15.04 sq.km in 1990 to 32.29 sq.km in 2022, indicating an expansion of 17.25 sq.km, potentially resulting from factors like reservoirs or changes in natural water bodies.

These changes in LULC have implications for the environment and land management. The significant increase in agriculture land may have effects on natural ecosystems and biodiversity, while the decrease in forest and bare land areas might affect climate and habitat. Further studies are necessary to understand the drivers behind these changes and to plan for sustainable land use and conservation strategies.

Conclusion and suggestions

This research work demonstrates the ability of GIS and Remote Sensing in capturing spatial-temporal data. Attempt was made to capture as accurate as possible five land use classes as they change through time. The analysis of land use and land cover (LULC) data for the Waghur Basin in two different years, 1990 and 2022, reveals significant changes in the region's landscape. These changes have far-reaching implications for the environment, biodiversity, and land management.

Between 1990 and 2022, the area of forest land decreased by 26.89 square kilometers. This reduction indicates a concerning trend of deforestation or natural habitat transformation. Preserving and restoring forested areas is critical for maintaining biodiversity and mitigating climate change.

Agriculture land saw a substantial increase of 401.68 square kilometers during the same period. This expansion is indicative of intensified agricultural activities and land conversion for farming. Sustainable agricultural practices are essential to minimize the environmental impact of such expansion.

The area of bare land decreased by 408.00 square kilometers, possibly due to urbanization, reforestation, or other land use changes. Urban growth should be carefully planned to balance development with environmental conservation.

Settlement areas grew by 15.96 square kilometers, reflecting modest urban expansion in the region. Managing urbanization is crucial to ensure that infrastructure development does not compromise the environment and natural resources.

Water bodies expanded by 17.25 square kilometers, which may result from reservoir construction or changes in natural water bodies. Preserving water resources and water quality is essential for ecosystem health and human well-being.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the analysis of the LULC data, the following suggestions are made:

- Initiatives to protect existing forested areas and undertake reforestation efforts should be prioritized to combat deforestation and preserve biodiversity.
- Encourage and support sustainable farming practices to ensure that agricultural expansion does not harm the environment, soil quality, or water resources.

- Urban expansion should be guided by well-defined urban planning policies to balance the need for infrastructure and housing with environmental preservation.
- Manage and monitor water resources effectively, especially in cases of reservoir construction, to ensure responsible water usage and the protection of aquatic ecosystems.
- Regular monitoring and assessment of LULC changes are essential to keep track of evolving land use patterns and to inform policy decisions and conservation efforts.

The Waghur Basin's LULC changes underscore the need for a comprehensive and sustainable approach to land management and conservation, ensuring that the region's natural resources and environment are preserved for future generations.

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